

A Crossover from First order transition to Second Order transition in $\text{Nd}_{1-x}\text{Cd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x = 0.2, 0.3$): Critical Behavior Study

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The magnetic and transport properties of perovskite manganites are controlled by bandwidth, which can be modified by the internal (doping) pressure at A-site, and therefore, first order transition to second order transition and/or vice versa through internal (doping) pressure is achievable. Generally, second order phase transitions are characterized by three well-defined constants termed as critical exponents, and These are encompassed by four types of universality models such as: the mean field, 3D Heisenberg, Tricritical mean field and 3D-Ising. Here, we report the doping effect of divalent cation Cd^{2+} at Nd-site of NdMnO_3 by magnetization measurements. $\text{Nd}_{1-x}\text{Cd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ (0.2) samples exhibits first order nature, whereas $\text{Nd}_{1-x}\text{Cd}_x\text{MnO}_3$ ($x = 0.3$) samples exhibit second order nature. It confirms a crossover from first order transition to second order transition while $x = 0.2$ to $x = 0.3$. The critical exponents are estimated of $x = 0.3$ sample has been analyzed using Arrott and Kouvel-Fisher plots. and the corresponding values are $\beta = 0.5176$, $\gamma = 1.0816$, $\delta = 3.45$ with $T_C = 85$ K. The estimated critical exponents of these samples are matched with mean free model, which can be explained by the existence of dipole-dipole interaction by the Cd doping which strengthens long range FM interactions between the spins. Hence, $\text{Nd}_{0.8}\text{Cd}_{0.2}\text{MnO}_3$ and $\text{Nd}_{0.7}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$ may be very good potential candidate for refrigeration technology.

FIG. (a) M_s and χ_0^{-1} of $\text{Nd}_{0.7}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$; (b) Kouvel-Fisher Plots for $\text{Nd}_{0.7}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$; (c) M vs H at $T = T_C$ for $\text{Nd}_{0.7}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$ [inset shows $\ln M$ vs $\ln H$ for δ]; (d) scaling plot below and above T_C for $\text{Nd}_{0.7}\text{Cd}_{0.3}\text{MnO}_3$.